

Learning Environments & Instructional Design Choices

Noureddine Mohamed Qassimi

Learning Environments & Instructional Design Choices

According to Seel et al. (2017), learning environments are intended to create learning opportunities responsive to the different learning categories established by Roth (1963, as cited in Seel, 2017) and Gagne's Nine Events of Instruction. On the one hand, Roth found that acquiring different skills requires different approaches to learning and instruction. On the other hand, Gagne established that successful learning environments must have well-defined learning objectives to which teaching and student action are closely tied. With these two main concepts in mind, Seel et al. (2017) propose that learning environments are constructive and student-led. Teachers organize materials and activities that initiate and facilitate learning and reflection. Hence, learning environments require stimulating learners' motivation, developing self-directed learning in each student, and constructing social skills of cooperation and communication among learners (Seel et al., 2017). These three characteristics of an exemplary environment influence the choice of instructional design that best meets the needs of the learning environment.

Stimulating Motivation in Learners

Inner motivation promotes a growth mindset in students and triggers ongoing learning processes. However, ensuring students remain motivated in complex learning environments is challenging. For students to develop “complex skills, deep conceptual understanding, and metacognitive skills such as self-regulated learning” (Gerjets & Hesse, 2007), teachers must create activities in which the conditions truly move learners to engage. This feature of the learning environment is relevant because motivated students are more likely to achieve the set goals or learning objectives. Likewise, students who feel motivated to engage will look for the personal satisfaction of reaching positive outcomes.

Learning through real-world experiences and problem-solving is one way of generating inner motivation. Nevertheless, motivation, unlike engagement, is challenging to measure because “observable indicators are not always accurate tangibly” (Kong, 2021). For

example, students who engage in rigorous programs, such as the International Baccalaureate, may constantly engage with the tasks provided but may not necessarily do it because they have inner motivation. Measuring this indicator can give us the impression that the choice of materials, pedagogy, teaching strategies, and assessments have effectively led to the achievement of the teaching objectives when they have not generated any real intrinsic motivation in the students.

Developing Self-Directed Learning

Students who take ownership of their learning become independent thinkers who question the world around them, are aware of their interests, evaluate content credibility, and demonstrate open-mindedness (Petro, 2017). Learning environments that aim for self-directed learning promote effectiveness by, among other things, raising awareness and providing opportunities for decision-making. Nevertheless, depending on the age of the learners, implementing self-directed learning in class can be rather challenging. For example, students may not know what to learn or take too long to decide how to conduct the learning process. Projects may be too long or too short, or students may have a problematic range of options. Others may opt for more straightforward projects rather than more challenging ones. When thinking of self-directed learning and instructional design, teachers must provide a plethora of materials for students to choose from and diverse learning experiences. Students building self-directing skills should be able to use knowledge to solve problems, acquire skills they can practice, and do so in groups or communities.

Building Social Skills

Seel et al. (2017) explain that effective learning environments should provide opportunities for “cooperation and communication, exploration, and identification of social relations within peer groups” (p. 5). Building social skills is relevant to students' learning goals and academic achievement, managing their emotions, and maintaining successful relationships in all walks of life. To promote this skill, teachers can design collaborative

activities in which groups of students must apply knowledge to solve problems or higher-order thinking skills. Such a learning environment must be backed by an instructional design choice that establishes goals for collaborative skills like sharing knowledge, discussing options, leading the group, and assigning roles (Keramida, 2021). Any collaborative activity must align with learning objectives and be part of the cultural environment. Effectively designing a social skills plan includes understanding the school culture and the needs of individual students, which can be challenging as it requires detailed observation and goal adjustment.

Conclusion

Learning environments need to consider the type of learning that will take place, such as problem-solving, procedural transferring, or behavior change (Roth 1963, as cited in Seel, 2017), to name a few. Likewise, they should include methods to stimulate students who understand the learning objectives, the instruction, and the tasks. Thus, learning environments are student-centered. They motivate the learners and develop self-directed learning and social skills. These three features of an adequate environment influence instructional design choices as they depend on the conditions of the school and the learner community.

References

- Abdullah, M. H. (2001). Self-Directed Learning. ERIC Digest.
<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED459458.pdf>
- Gerjets, P., Hesse, F. (2007). When are powerful learning environments effective? The role of learner activities and students' conceptions of educational technology. *International Journal of Educational Research*, Elsevier, 2004, 41(6), pp.445-465. at:
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2005.08.011>
- Keramida, M. (2021, May 12). Social Learning In Instructional Design: Practical Tips To Design Effective Collaborative eLearning Activities. eLearning Industry.
<https://elearningindustry.com/social-learning-in-instructional-design-practical-tips-to-design-effective-collaborative-elearning-activities>
- Kong Y. (2021). The Role of Experiential Learning on Students' Motivation and Classroom Engagement. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 771272.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.771272>
- Petro, L. (2017, April 11). How to Put Self-Directed Learning to Work in Your Classroom. Edutopia. <https://www.edutopia.org/discussion/how-put-self-directed-learning-work-your-classroom>
- Seel, N. M., Lehmann, T., Blumschien, P., & Podolskiy, O. A. (2017). *Instructional design for learning: Theoretical foundations*.
https://www.google.com/books/edition/Instructional_Design_for_Learning/UmCwDgAAQBAJ?hl=en&gbpv=1&printsec=frontcover